

**PHARMACOLOGICAL, PHYTOCHEMICAL AND SYSTEMATICAL
ANALYSIS OF *ECHINOPS ECHINATUS* ROXB.
(A HERBAL MEDICINAL PLANT)**

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ABSTRACT

Echinops echinatus Roxb. (*E. echinatus*), commonly known as “Usnakantaka,” is a xerophytic herbaceous plant traditionally used as a stimulant to treat use the term Sexual debility in Indian traditional systems of medicine. The roots, leaves, fruit, and bark are extensively used in folk medicine as well as in Ayurveda. Also, the plant shows a wide range of pharmacological activities such as antifungal, analgesic, diuretic, reproductive, hepatoprotective, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, wound-healing, antipyretic, and antibacterial properties. Among the several active constituents, apigenin, apigenin-7-O-glucoside, echinaticin, 5,7-dihydroxy-8,4'-dimethoxy-flavanone-5-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-7-O - β -D-arabinopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- β -D-glucopyranoside are the most important in terms of reported pharmacological activities. The current review focuses on the updated information from various scientific studies and reports available in the context of the phytoconstituents and pharmacology of this plant. This review also provides adequate information about the use of this plant in an Indian system of medicine, Ayurveda.

Key words: Apigenin, Ayurveda, echinaticin, *Echinops echinatus*, Usnakantaka.

INTRODUCTION

Bramhadandi common name of *Echinops echinatus* Roxb is a pubescent annual herb of 1-3ft height with branches generally spreading from the base. The species are found practically throughout India and useful for the treatment of various ailments in the Indian system of medicine. This literature search acknowledges that the plant is a popular remedy for a variety of ailments and very little effort have been made to check its efficacy through scientific screenings in animal model. The present review focused on various folk, Ayurvedic uses, pharmacognostical, phytochemical and pharmacological studies conducted on *Echinops echinatus* Roxb, and also highlight unexplored potential of it.

Vernacular names

English:	Indian Globe Thistle
Hindi:	Gokhru, Uthkanta, Utakatira
Gujarati :	Shuliyo, Utkanto, Utkato
Sanskrit:	Kantalu, Kantaphala, Utati, Utkantaka
Sindhi:	Dammai
Urdu:	Barham dandi, Labh, Unt katara
Telugu:	Brahmadandi
Kannada:	Brahmadande
Marathi:	Utkatar, Kate-chendu

Systematic Position

Kingdom :	Plantae
Phylum :	Magnoliophyta
Class:	Magnolipsida
Subclass:	Asteridae
Order:	Asterales
Family:	Asteraceae
Genus:	<i>Echinops</i>
Species:	<i>echinatus</i>

Distribution:

More or less throughout India and Afghanistan.

Leaves:

Alternately arranged oblong, deeply pinnatifid leaves are 7-12 cm long.

Flowers:

Flower-heads occur in solitary white spherical balls, 3-5 cm across. Petals of the tiny white flowers are 5 mm long. Flowers are surrounded by straight, strong and white. Odour is pungent and taste is bitter.

Description:

Echinops echinatus Roxb,(Asteraceae) is a pubescent annual herb of 1-3ft height with branches widely spreading from the base. Is a perennial, 40-100cm high, Stems are simple or branching from the base, sparsely cobweb by-canescence. Leaves are lanceolate or oblong-lanceolate. It has short, stout stems, branching from

the base, covered with white cottony hair. The species is found practically throughout India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, etc.

PHYTOCHEMICALS PRESENT IN THE *ECHINOPS ECHINATUS*:-

Echinops plant was reported to possess variety of compounds belonging to various classes like: alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, lipids, steroids and polyacetylenes. Many literature survey revealed different pharmacological activities of Echinops plant like, antibacterial activity, antifungal), antioxidant activity, protective effects on testosterone-induced prostatic hyperplasia, hepatoprotective and anti-ulcerogenic activity. Flavonoids (Figure 1) are a class of natural products that gains interest due to the different pharmacological activities since Flavonoids are powerful antioxidants against free radicals and are described as free-radical scavengers. This activity is attributed to their hydrogen-donating ability. Indeed, the phenolic groups of flavonoids serve as a source of a readily available "H" atoms such that the subsequent radicals produced can be delocalized over the flavonoids structure. Also flavonoids have anti-inflammatory action, antibacterial, anti-fungal effect.

Flavonoids protect the gastrointestinal mucosa from lesions produced by various experimental ulcer models and against different necrotic agents, also they possess anticarcinogenic effects since they can interfere with the initiation, development and progression of cancer by the modulation of cellular proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, angiogenesis and metastasis.

Figure 1. Basic structure of flavonoids

The most important flavonoids glycoside isolated from different species of Echinops plant are listed in the following table (Table 1). This study was emphasized on the isolation and identification of flavonoids glycoside found in the Iraqi species of Echinops plant by column Chromatography (CC), using glass column packed with polyamide 6 slurry in ethanol.

Table 1.
Flavonoids glycoside isolated from different species of Echinopsplant

Flavonoids	Sources
Kaempferol, kaempferol 4'-methylether, kaempferol 7-methylether, kaempferol 3-O- alpha- L- rhamnoside, myrecetin-3-O-alpha-L-rhamnoside	<i>Echinops echinatus</i>
Dihydroquercetin-4'-methyl ether, 5,7 -8,4 -dimethoxyflavanone-5-O- -L-rhamnopyranosyl- 7-O- -Darabinopyranosyl-(1 4)-O- -D-glucopyranoside	<i>Echinops echinatus</i>
Silymarine	<i>Echinops tenuisectus</i>
Quercetin	<i>Echinops tenuisectus</i>
Apigenin (4',5,7-trihydroxyflavone, luteolin)	<i>Echinops niveus</i>
Kaempferol	<i>Echinops galalensis and Echinops hussoni</i>
Apigenin, hispidulin, 5,4dihydroxy flavone and apigenin 7-O- glucoside	<i>Echinops spinosissimus</i>
Apigenin	<i>Echinops latifolius</i>
Kaempferol, myricetin	<i>Echinops spinosus</i>
Neoflavonoid nivetin	<i>Echinops niveus</i>
Apigenin, apigenin-7-O-glucoside, echinacin, and echinaticin	<i>Echinops echinatus</i>

Aerial parts of the plant contain alkaloids, **echinopsine**, **echinopsidine** and **echinozolinone**. **Taraxasterol acetate**, **Apigenin** and its derivatives, **echinacin** and **echinaticin**.

2',5,7-trihydroxy-3,6-dimethoxyflavone-7-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-[1-4]-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside is reported from the seeds of *Echinops echinatus*. Apigenin, apigenin 7-O-glucoside, and a new acylflavoneglucoside named echitin (I) were isolated from *Echinopsechinatus* flowers.

A minor alkaloid 7-hydroxyechinozolinone (I) is reported from the flowers of *E. echinatus*

An antiinflammatory active flavanone glycoside 5,7-dihydroxy-8,4'-dimethoxyflavanone-5-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-7-O- β -D-arabinopyranosyl-(1-4)-O- β -D-glucopyranoside A along with a known compd. dihydroquercetin-4'-Methoxy ether is also reported from the leaves of *Echinops echinatus*. A minor alkaloid 7-hydroxy echinozolinone (I) is reported from the flowers of *E. echinatus*. Four phenolic compounds. apigenin, apigenin 7-O-glucoside, echinacin(I), and echinaticin (II), were reported from *E. echinatus* Roxb. Isomeric acyl flavone glycosides echinacin (I) and echinaticin (II) are reported from *E. echinatus*. Chaudhuri PK26 (1997) isolated Echinozolinone an alkaloid from *Echinops echinatus*. In addition to echinopsine and echinopsidine, a new alkaloid, echinozolinone, has been identified in *Echinops echinatus* as 3(2-hydroxyethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone from its spectral data. Besides apigenin 7-O-glucoside, a new

acylated l&one has been identified in *Echinops echinatus* as apigenin 7-O- (4''-ciscouyl~e from spectral and chemical analysis.

PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES AND MEDICINAL USE OF *ECHINOPS ECHINATUS*:

Antifungal activity:

Four phenolic compounds, viz., apigenin, apigenin-7-O-glucoside, echinacin, and echinaticin, were isolated from the whole plant of *Echinops echinatus* Roxb. The latter two compounds were isolated for the first time. The two derivatives echinacinpermethyl ether and apigenin5, 4'-dimethyl ether were obtained by methylation of echinacin and apigenin-7-O-glucoside permethylate, respectively. All the compounds were assayed against germination of conidia of *Alternariatenuissima* (Kunz. ex Pers.) Wiltshire, which incites leaf blight disease in pigeon pea (*Cajanuscajan.*). All showed high efficacy against the pathogen at concentrations ranging from 25 to 150⁻¹mL µg Echinacin, which was highly effective at 150⁻¹, is considered the most promising of these compounds and its use as a control measure against *Alternaria* blight of pigeon pea under field conditions has been suggested.

Apigenin R¹-R²-R³-H
Apigenin-7-O-glucoside R¹-Glc, R²-R³-H

Taraxasterol acetate

Echinacin

Ethyl palmitate

Echinacin

5,7-Dihydroxy-8,8'-dimethoxyflavanone-5-O-α-L-rhamnosyl-7-O-β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→4)-O-β-D-glucopyranoside

Anti-inflammatory:

Anti-inflammatory studies were conducted on an ethanol extract of *Echinops echinatus* whole plant. The extract effectively inhibited the acute inflammation induced in rats by carrageenan, formaldehyde, adjuvant and the chronic arthritis induced by formaldehyde and adjuvant. The extract was more effective parenterally than orally. The toxicity studies showed reasonable safety warranting further studies.

Analgesic:

The Analgesic potential of methanolic extracts of the aerial parts and roots was assessed in albino rats using Hot plate, Tail immersion and Tail flick models. The reaction time was the parameter of the study. Pentazocine was used as standard. The results indicate that methanolic extracts at 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg body weight shows a significant increase in reaction time when compared to control. Both the extracts show significant Analgesic activity. From the present study it may

be concluded that the constituents present in methanolic extracts may be responsible for Analgesic activity.

Diuretic:

The diuretic potential of methanolic extracts of the aerial parts and roots was assessed in albino rats using in-vivo Lipschitz test model. The volumes of urine, urinary concentration of sodium and potassium ions were the parameters of the study. Frusemide was used as standard. The results indicate that methanolic extracts at 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg bodyweight shows a significant increase in the urine volume and electrolyte excretion when compared to control. Both the extracts show significant diuretic activity. From the present study it may be concluded that the constituents present in methanolic extracts may be responsible for diuretic activity.

Protective effect:

E. echinatus extracts attenuated the increase in the prostatic/body weight ratio induced by testosterone. Butanolic fraction of ethanolic extract exhibited the best activity. Testosterone levels measured weekly and prostatespecific antigen (PSA) levels. Further histological studies have shown a considerable improvement in medicine.

CONCLUSION

Echinops echinatus Roxb, has been in use since ancient times to treat widerange of diseases in traditional system medicine. The present review provides information regarding scientific and conventional use of the plant. It is an attempt to unite the relevant available information of the species and proven its antidiabetic, antihypertensive, analgesic, antiinflammatory, antifungal activity, hepatoprotective, antifertility, antioxidant, diuretic and protective effects. From the above information it is concluded that it is a unique natural product for the development of medicines against various diseases and also for the development of industrial products.

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